

New Antiplasmodial Derivative from a Structural Modification of Quinuclidin of Quinin J.N.

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ABSTRACT

A new derivative **1** has been synthesized from 6-méthoxy-4-(1'-méthoxy-2''-(8''-vinylquinuclidinyl)) quinolin known as quinin. The synthesized compound has been characterized using proton, carbon-13, DEPT-135, 2D-COSY and 2D-HMBC Nuclear Magnetic Resonance data. The evaluation of its *in vivo* antiplasmodial activities above the NMRI mice shows that the derivative **1** is most active than its analogue quinin. The derivative **1** shows a parasitemia rate of -0,68% against *Plasmodium bergeri* administered to the NMRI mice, whereas the parasitemia rate of quinine amount to 0,23% under the same conditions.

Keywords: Quinin, New derivative, higher *in vivo* antiplasmodial activities

INTRODUCTION

With 300 or 500 millions patients and 1,5 to 2,7 millions deaths each year, malaria remains the most important tropical disease. Eighty per cent of cases are registered in sub-Saharan Africa, where malaria concerns in the majority young children under five years of age and pregnant women^{1,2}. The parasite is the plasmodium from which one distinguishes 4 different species³. In order to fight malaria, different compounds with different activities have been brought on the market, among them chloroquin, amodiaquin, quinin...All these compounds were, despite their different activities, very effective arms against the malaria parasites; but their regulations without control, and therefore their misuses have favoured the emergence of antiplasmodial drugs resistant pathogens. Amodiaquin, for instance, can be used nowadays for the treatment of malaria only in combination with artesunate. It is an aminoquinolin, which is only active against the chloroquino-resistant parasites⁴. Chloroquin has been declared ineffective against the *plasmodium* by WHO^{5,9}. Even in the presence of quinin, the parasites develop more and more resistance. All these remain a great obstacle in the control of malaria in the regions where this disease is endemic². Owing to the increasing resistance to these antiplasmodial compounds, we have thought that instead of a simply abandoning of these drugs, which have shown their effect during several years, to proceed if possible via structural modifications of these antiplasmodial drugs by synthesis and to subject the obtained products to *in vivo* antiplasmodial screening above the NMRI mice. It is in this frame that we have synthesized the compound **1** from quinin. The synthesis of 6-méthoxy-4-(1',2'-dihydroxy-4''-(2''-vinylpiperidinyll)) quinolin through a ring opening by SN2 pull mechanism accompanied of the *in vivo* evaluation of its antiplasmodial activities above the NMRI mice expressed by the parasitemia rate remain important contributions of this work.

Synthesis of 6-méthoxy-4-(1',2'-dihydroxypropyl-4''-(2''-vinylpiperidinyll)) quinolin **1**

Quinin derivative **1** has been obtained by a strong acid catalysed reaction of quinin at lower temperature (-10°C). The addition of NaOH to pH 8 led up to get the derivative **1** as pale yellow crystals in good yield after precipitation through a ring opening by an SN2 pull mechanism.

The chemical equation can be summarized in this manner as illustrated in the scheme I:

EXPERIMENTAL PART

TLC: aluminium sheets silica gel (60 F254 Merck).

¹H- and ¹³C-NMR spectra: Bruker-WM 600 (600 and 125MHz, resp.), tetramethylsilane and CD₃COCD₃ with respect to TMS als internal references; δ in ppm and J in Hz.

6-Méthoxy-4-(1',2'-dihydroxypropyl-4''-(2''-vinylpiperidinyll)) quinolin (1**).** To a stirred mixture of 9,1ml (217,1 mmol) concentrated nitric acid and 9,1ml (170,2mmol) concentrated sulfuric acid at -10°C was added 10g (30,8mmol) of quinin by portion of 1g all five minutes. The solution was stirred for 10h and keep at -10°C. After 10h, the solution was brought back at room temperature, and a solution of 5N NaOH was then added until pH 8. The resulting precipitate was filtered and washed with distilled

water until pH 7 of waste water. The solid residue was at last dried during a week: **1** was isolated (9g, 69%) as weak yellow crystals. ¹H-NMR: Table 1. ¹³C-NMR: Table 2

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Chemical results

The progress of the reaction for obtaining quinin derivate **1** has been monitored by thin layer chromatography. Quinin shows an Rf value of 0,37, whereas its derivative **1** has an Rf value of 0,52

with ethanol as eluent. This led us up to say that there has been effective a reaction which has given a product whose the structure is fully supported by ¹H-NMR, ¹³C- NMR, DEPT-135, 2D-COSY and 2D-HMBC Nuclear Magnetic Resonance data.

The protons H-C(19) and H-C(15) are not visible in the proton spectrum, because they lie under the peak of the solvent. But, in the 2D-NMR, clear correlations are present between the concerned C-atoms and the peaks of the solvent.

Table1. ¹H-NMR Data ^{a)} (CD₃COCD₃) of the quinin derivative **1** at 600 MHz; δ in ppm and J in Hz, internal standard TMS

OH	11,80	OH or NH	5,74	H-C(16')	3,37
H-C(1)	8,75	H-C(21)	5,12	H-C(19)	2,8
H-C(8)	7,95	H-C(21)	4,97	H-C(13)	2,31
H-C(2)	7,76	H-C(16)	4,33	H-C(15)	2,26
H-C(5)	7,41	H-C(10)	4,00	H-C(14)	2,22
H-C(7)	7,34	H-C(12)	3,76	H-C(15')	2,0
H-C(11)	6,22	H-C(18)	3,75	H-C(13')	1,61
H-C(20)	5,86	H-C(18')	3,40		

J(1,2)	4,4
J(8,7)	9,2
J(2,1)	4,4
J(5,7)	2,8
J(7,8)	9,2
J(7,5)	2,8
J(21,20)	17,2
J(21',20)	10,5

Table 2. ¹³C-NMR Data a) (CD₃COCD₃) of the quinin derivate **1** at 125 MHz; δ in ppm, internal standard TMS

C(6)	159,66	C(7)	123,40	C(18)	55,37
C(1)	148,23	C(2)	120,01	C(16)	44,94
C(3)	145,83	C(21)	116,85	C(19)	38,41
C(9)	145,37	C(5)	101,30	C(14)	28,33
C(20)	139,75	C(11)	67,66	C(15)	25,22
C(8)	132,64	C(12)	60,88	C(13)	18,93
C(4)	126,90	C(10)	56,99		

Table 3. ¹³C- DEPT-135 Data a) (CD₃COCD₃) of the quinin derivate **1** at 125 MHz; δ in ppm, internal standard TMS

C(6)	-	C(4)	-	C(12)	-CH=	C(15)	-CH ₂ -
C(1)	-CH=	C(7)	-CH=	C(10)	-CH ₃	C(13)	-CH ₂ -
C(3)	-	C(2)	-CH=	C(18)	-CH ₂ -		
C(9)	-	C(21)	-CH ₂ -	C(16)	-CH ₂ -		
C(20)	-CH=	C(5)	-CH=	C(19)	-CH=		
C(8)	-CH=	C(11)	-CH=	C(14)	-CH=		

Fig. 1. 2D-COSY of **1** recorded at 600 MHz

Fig.2. 2D-HMBC of **1** recorded at 600 MHz

In comparing the $^1\text{H-NMR}$ and $^{13}\text{C-NMR}$ data of the quinolin derivative **1** and the quinin⁶, it is evident that the quinolin part remains unchanged in both molecules. The changes are perceived in the quinuclidin ring, where the presence of a large band with an integration of a proton at 5,74 ppm in the proton NMR is seen, indicating the presence of a proton near of a heteroatom, which can be in this case the oxygen or the nitrogen. Moreover, this structural modification of quinuclidin is to perceive by observing the carbon (13) of the product. This carbon is to find in a highfield shift (18,93ppm) in comparison with that of quinin (27,70ppm). This can be explained in the fact that the carbon (13), near of this reactions site, knows an additional screening due to the introduction of a substituent in position (12).

All this leads us up to say that there has been an acid catalyzed quinuclidin ring opening by $\text{S}_{\text{N}}2$ pull mechanism⁷. Driving force is the protonated heteroatom, which breaks up the link in ring and attracts a nucleophil agent from reverse side⁷. This type of mechanism is present also in the case of a transdihydroxylation of an alcene with a peracid, where it observes an opening of protonated

oxiran owing to an attack of nucleophil agent¹⁴. The particularity that we have in our case is that the ring opening takes places in a more than three membered ring.

After the determination of the structure of the synthesized product **1**, the *in vivo* antiparasmodial activities of the product **1** have been evaluated in relation to that one of the quinin in order to complete this work.

In vivo antiparasmodial Tests

6-Méthoxy-4-(1',2'-dihydroxypropyl-4'-(2''-vinylpiperidiny)) quinolin **1** has been evaluated for its antiparasmodial activities above the NMRI mice grown at the Institut National de Recherches biomédicales/ Kinshasa, DRC and infected with *plasmodium bergeri*. Different doses have been administered to the different mice, and the parasitemia has been followed during six days of treatment.

At the maximal concentration (0,80mmol/l) for the quinin and its derivate **1**, this last compound **1** showed an antiparasmodial activity more than quinin (-0,68% vs 0,23% of parasitemia rate), which was used as the reference substance.

CONCLUSION

The draft of new antiparasmodial agent and its synthesis through an acid catalyzed quinuclidin ring opening by $\text{S}_{\text{N}}2$ pull mechanism from quinin are important contributions of this work.

The current results show that the quinolin derivative **1** is *in vivo* more active than the quinin against the parasmodial agents.

In the view of these results, we can say that the antiparasmodial compounds, which lose more and more their effect, can be used again by structural modification through a good oriented synthesis.

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REFERENCES

1. D. Adamson, *Bref aperçu du rapport de l'OMS et de l'UNICEF sur le paludisme en Afrique*, Ed. Africa malaria, Oxford, 2003
2. D. Joy, X. Feng et al, *Early origin and recent expansion of plasmodium falciparum*, Ed. Sciences, 300, pp.318-321, 2003
3. H. Ginsburg, H. Krugliak, *Biochemical pharmacology*, 43, N° 1, pp.63-70, 1992
4. CH. Kascula, T.J. Egan, *J Med Chem*, 45, pp. 3531-3539, 2002
5. O.M.S, *utilisation des antipaludiques : Rapport d'une consultation informelle de l'OMS*, Ed. C. Lebrun, p.156, suisse,2001
6. M. Hesse, H. Meier, B. Zeeh, « *Spectroskopische Methoden in der Organischen Chemie* », Ed. Georg thieme, Stuttgart, 1995
7. E. Breitmaier, G. Jung, « *Organische Chemie II* », Ed. Georg Thieme, p.162, Stuttgart, 1995
8. A. Lesich, *molecular modeling: principes and applications*, prentice Hall, 2001
9. www.Wikipedia.de

10. F.D. Divergent, *journal of American chemical society*, 127, pp. 14785-14803, 2005
11. [11] D. T. Davies, *Chimie des hétérocycles aromatiques*, De Boeck university, 1992
12. L. F. Tietze, T. Eicher, « *Reaktionen und synthesen* », Ed. Georg Thieme, Stuttgart, 1991
13. C. Porntip, W. Praon et al, *antimicrobial agents and chemotherapy*, 37, pp. 403-406, 1993
14. E. Breitmeier, G. Jung, “ *Organische Chemie I* “, Ed. Georg Thieme, p.63, Stuttgart, 1994

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